

*On the Domestic Several Business Women's Clothing Brand Clothing Quality Analysis of
the AHP and Fuzzy Comprehensive Evaluation*

Arrived Date
25.10.2020

Accepted Date
27.10.2020

Published Date
31.10.2020

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ABSTRACT

Contemporary white-collar women are outstanding in this era, and their professional thinking minds are also bringing unprecedented shocks to this society. Working in society, they must use all possible means such as inner powerful abilities and beautiful outer images to win opportunities for survival and development in this talented society, and show their charm. Therefore, the requirements for business dress will be much higher. This article selects seven brands of business women's clothing, combines the needs of white-collar women to determine the factors that affect the choice of clothing, and analyzes the quality of clothing through the combination of AHP and fuzzy comprehensive evaluation. Through the analysis of the research results, it can be concluded that the white-collar women's choice of clothing and the design emphasis of various brand merchants on business women's clothing are summarized. The research results will help white-collar women to more clearly choose clothing brands that can meet their needs. These commercial women's clothing brands can also learn from it to control their market positioning and the future direction of clothing design, and at the same time help the company provide a theoretical basis for improving the quality of branded clothing and increasing market share.

INTRODUCTION

In international clothing consumption research, the main consumer group is female consumers aged 20-35. According to statistics, the current domestic female consumer group occupies a huge market, with more than 500 million. The "her economy" consumer industry surrounding the female consumer group involves a wide range of industries. According to the "China Women's Consumption Survey Report" jointly released by Ruiwen and SPO, from the perspective of consumer subjects, the proportion of urban women in China is much higher than that of developed countries such as the United States, Britain, and France, accounting for nearly 70%. This means that urban women with independent sources of income have strong spending power, and female consumption will become the main force in future consumption growth. In the consumption of young women's clothing, the white-collar class has a high level of consumption, so they also have higher requirements for business wear necessary for work.

Literature

Domestic research on white-collar women's attitude and pursuit of clothing has been conducted since 2001. I think (Ping, 2004) summed up a sentence that is correct: "Women's needs for clothing have been transformed from a purely physiological requirement. It has evolved to a situation where psychological requirements are the main and physiological requirements." In the early days, (Dan, 2013) emphasized that white-collar women in the new era pursued the double satisfaction of materiality and embodying their own value and respect. They generally have their own dressing tastes and fancy the influence of the brand. At the same time, due to long-term consumption, they will form a preference for a certain brand and will not blindly follow the trend of choice (Guangyu, 2019). Since

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then, both (Jie,2016) sociological analysis of the conspicuous consumption of white-collar women born in the 1990s and Cai Ying's (2017). study of the consumption of Korean women born in the 1980s have pointed out a common feature of female consumption. The characteristic is irrational consumption, that is, conspicuous consumption. (Dengming, 2014) gave an explanation on conspicuous consumption. (Guopeng, 2018) analyzed the research and application of business casual clothing brand product portfolio, and recognized that the income and spending power of women in the workplace make them have higher requirements in terms of business wear, personalization, and the essence of clothing products. And brand value are their consumer demands (Jiao, 2019). (Bixuan et al., 2017) gave a fuzzy comprehensive evaluation of the wearing and self-cleaning performance of wool/ramie fabrics. There is a fuzzy relationship between the indexes and the comprehensive evaluation results (Stephenson, 1986) and the fuzzy comprehensive evaluation can transform qualitative into quantitative Evaluation, increase its correlation with subjective evaluation, which can effectively evaluate systems with complex relationships (Yi, Kunyao, 2010)

At the beginning of the 20th century, (Dr. Zhu Lan, Bing, 2009) believed that quality is not a fixed concept, it is dynamic, developing, and comprehensive. It is the pursuit of the best combination of performance, cost, delivery time, service and other factors. Therefore, we can easily relate that the quality of clothing is also dynamic, and its evaluation indicators will have obvious fuzzy and non-quantitative characteristics, and it is difficult to use general mathematical methods for quantitative evaluation. The uncertainty of this concept and the non-quantification of evaluation are very suitable for processing by the fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method in fuzzy mathematics. Since the American scholar Professor Zadeh proposed the concept of fuzzy set (Zadeh,1965) fuzzy mathematics theory has developed rapidly in recent decades, and the fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method based on fuzzy mathematics theory has also achieved great results. It has been widely used successfully in the engineering field (Shihao, Wenhua, Dunbing, et. al. 2010)

Purpose of the research

Based on the status quo and development trends of domestic women's employment and status, this article selects the most popular thin suit among the business wear essential for urban white-collar women as the object of this research on clothing quality. From the psychological characteristics of urban white-collar women and Starting from the dress motive, choosing appropriate evaluation indicators, and using clear data results to show who has the advantage of several well-known domestic business women's clothing brands, is more in line with the choice of white-collar women. The research results aim to provide theoretical guidance for consumers to rationally choose their own branded clothing, so that many business women's clothing brands are inspired, realize their own shortcomings and advantages, and reconsider their future development plans.

APPLICATION OF AHP-FUZZY COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION METHOD IN QUALITY EVALUATION OF BRAND BUSINESS WOMEN'S CLOTHING

Determination of reference for selection and evaluation of business women's clothing brands

Regarding the choice of brands, there are many women's wear brands that are currently active in the apparel market and are well known and loved by the public. In particular, some European and American fashion brands are more popular with capital women. However, only Chinese brand clothing is selected for comparative analysis. Based on the questionnaire survey of Lemei website, seven clothing brands are selected from the most popular Chinese business women's clothing brands selected through online voting as the research of this paper. unit. The seven clothing brands are: JIAFEN, Shangying, EVA OUXIU, Yibeiqi, Sunview, DITIZI, and WHITE COLLAR.

Business women's clothing is a large category, and its analysis needs to be narrowed down to a specific type of clothing for targeted evaluation and analysis. This article mainly refers to the following two points for the selection of business women's clothing. One is the working environment of white-collar women, regardless of spring, summer, autumn and winter, the corporate office will provide a suitable temperature; the second is their leisure life, informal communication and meeting with customers after get off work , Attending banquets, gatherings of friends, etc. Due to time waiting for

some uncertain factors, thin suits are generally a choice. Therefore, the thin suit that is most popular and most suitable for white-collar women will be selected as the research object.

Establish a set of factors for evaluating the quality of business women's clothing

According to Luo Jie's consumer psychology analysis of white-collar women in China, we know that the psychology of showing off is very common among them. The dressing needs of white-collar women at this stage: 1) The pertinence of status and position varies with their occupation and class. The emphasis is on appropriateness and comfort; 2) Rigorous fashion, which reflects that fashion is white-collar women's clothing from rigor. A major feature is that it should not give people a feeling of flirty while performing fashion. A rigorous work attitude must also be reflected; 3) The utility of convenient activities must meet the basic functions of clothing, and the style should be simple and generous, comfortable and fit And slightly loose cut, easy to move; 4) the scientific use of fabrics, can not use a variety of artistic exaggeration methods to enrich the image of the clothing, so in order to make the shape simple, the details of the decoration are not exaggerated and cumbersome, the special properties of the fabric should be used To enrich its appearance.

In summary, after understanding the basic psychology of white-collar women and their motivations for business wear, this article has determined the fabric comfort, color matching, and clothing accessories related to the clothing itself, as well as the rigorous fashion of the society. Self-centeredness and style-specific indicators are used as the evaluation index system for studying the quality of business women's clothing, that is, the factor set.

Determine the weight of indicators at all levels with the aid of AHP method

Constructing a hierarchical structure

The first step is to build a clothing quality evaluation index system, divide it into layers, and establish a clear stepped evaluation index system. According to the selected factor set, the hierarchical structure shown in Table 1 can be established:

Table 1 Hierarchical structure of quality evaluation indicators for business women's clothing

Target layer	Quality Evaluation Index System of Thin Suits for Business Women (A)	
Criterion layer	Self indexB ₁	Social indicatorsB ₂
Index layer	Fabric comfortB ₁₁	Rigorous fashionB ₂₁
	Color matchingB ₁₂	EgocentricityB ₂₂
	Clothing accessoriesB ₁₃	Style pertinenceB ₂₃

Index weights at the evaluation criterion level

The AHP method is used to determine the weight of the clothing quality evaluation index. According to the AHP ratio scale, the survey, own professional knowledge and practical experience are combined to compare and analyze the second-level evaluation indicators under the two major first-level indicators and carry out the indicators. The relative importance between the two is assigned, and the comparison judgment matrix is given, and then the calculation is performed to determine the weight of each evaluation index. The calculation results are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2 A-B judgment matrix and relative weight

A	Self index	Social indicators	Normalized weight
Self index	1	1/5	0.1667
Social indicators	5	1	0.8334
λ_{\max}		1.0000	
CI		0.9999	$\Sigma = 1$
CR			

The calculation process is as follows:

(1) Record the judgment matrix $B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1/5 \\ 5 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$, and normalize it with the sum-product method to

$$\text{get } \bar{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/6 & 1/6 \\ 5/6 & 5/6 \end{bmatrix}.$$

(2) Perform matrix \bar{B} row sum operation to obtain matrix $\bar{W} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3333 \\ 1.6667 \end{bmatrix}$, and \bar{W} then normalize to obtain $W = [0.1667 \quad 0.8334]$;

That is, the weight vector of criterion layer B relative to target layer A: $W = [0.1667 \quad 0.8334]$.

(3) Solve the A-B judgment matrix

$$\lambda_{\max} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} w_j}{w_i} \right] = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1 \times \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{5} \times \frac{5}{6}}{0.3333} + \frac{5 \times \frac{1}{6} + 1 \times \frac{5}{6}}{1.6667} \right) = 1.0000 \quad (1)$$

(4) Consistency test: Consistency index $CI = (\lambda_{\max} - n)/(n - 1) = 0.9999$, according to the average random consistency value in Table 3-1, we can see that when $n=2$, $RI=0.00$.

Evaluation index layer index weight

(1) Calculation of the weights of the secondary indicators under the primary indicator B1

As shown in the following table 3-3, the relative importance of the secondary evaluation index of its own index is given, and the calculation results of the weight of each evaluation index are shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3 The second-level index weight table under the first-level index's own index B1

B ₁	Fabric comfortB ₁₁	Color matchingB ₁₂	Clothing accessoriesB ₁₃	Normalized weight
Fabric comfortB ₁₁	1	3	5	0.6333
Color matchingB ₁₂	1/3	1	3	0.2605
Clothing accessoriesB ₁₃	1/5	1/3	1	0.1062
λ_{\max}	1.3155			$\Sigma = 1$
CI	-0.8423			
CR	-0.14522			

The consistency ratio $CR = 0.14522 < 0.1$, therefore, the judgment matrix B1 is consistent, and the relative weight of each evaluation index is reasonable.

Similarly, according to the second-level index weights under the first-level index B2, the results of solving the weights of each evaluation index are shown in Table 4:

Table 4 The second-level indicator weight table under the first-level indicator social indicator B2

B ₂	Rigorous fashionB ₂₁	EgocentricityB ₂₂	Style pertinenceB ₂₃	Normalized weight
Rigorous fashionB ₂₁	1	1/5	3	0.1932
EgocentricityB ₂₂	5	1	7	0.7235
Style pertinenceB ₂₃	1/3	1/7	1	0.0833
λ_{\max}	1.2493			
CI	-0.8754			$\sum = 1$
CR	-1.5093			

The consistency ratio CR=-1.5093<0.1, the judgment matrix B2 is consistent, and the relative weight of each evaluation index is reasonable.

Comprehensive calculations to obtain the comprehensive weight of the thin suit quality evaluation indicators, as shown in Table 5:

Table 5 Quality Evaluation Index System of Business Women's Clothing (A) and Index Weight Distribution

First level indicator	First-level weight	Secondary indicators	Secondary weight value
Self indexB ₁	0.1667	Fabric comfortB ₁₁	0.6333
		Color matchingB ₁₂	0.2605
		Clothing accessoriesB ₁₃	0.1062
Social indicatorsB ₂	0.8334	Social indicatorsB ₂₁	0.1932
		EgocentricityB ₂₂	0.7235
		Style pertinenceB ₂₃	0.0833

Establish a comment set for clothing quality evaluation

This article divides the evaluation set into 4 levels:

$$V = \{v_1 \ v_2 \ v_3 \ v_4\} = \{\text{excellent good moderate poor}\}$$

A comprehensive judgment should be made for each identified sub-factor. The selected quality indicators are quantitative and qualitative. Therefore, in the specific evaluation, it is necessary to divide the quantitative indicators into different intervals according to the characteristics of the enterprise, divide the qualitative indicators into different levels, and give a unified standard score value.

Fuzzy hierarchical evaluation of each company

It can be seen from 3.3 that the weight of the evaluation index, that is, the weight of each factor is as follows:

$$W_1 = [0.6333 \ 0.2605 \ 0.1062] \quad W_2 = [0.1932 \ 0.7235 \ 0.0833] \quad W = [0.1667 \ 0.8334]$$

According to the domestic research literature, we can extract the information about the psychology of showing off. White-collar women pay more attention to the realization of self-centeredness in clothing consumption, which is also confirmed in the calculation of the weight of each quality evaluation index by the analytic hierarchy process. . Therefore, we can see that social indicators are very important, and the egocentricity in social indicators occupies a pivotal position. Based on this, we can predict that if the brand attaches great importance to the self-centered factor, its clothing quality will be very popular and recognized by customers.

For this social survey, the questionnaire was sent to women in different positions in a number of larger companies in the form of mailboxes. After statistics, the statistical results in the following tables were obtained. The survey data in this article adopts a sample survey method. Due to the limitation of samples and the scope of survey data collection, the data only represents the survey time and the basic conditions of the population, services and current survey purposes, and provide basic references for the market and customers.

According to the results of the survey and statistics of the Jiafen brand, each index in Jiafen Company is evaluated according to the standard scores and comment sets of the following evaluation index system, and a fuzzy evaluation matrix of two first-level indicators is obtained:

$$R_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.47 & 0.3 & 0.23 & 0 \\ 0.33 & 0.53 & 0.13 & 0 \\ 0.43 & 0.37 & 0.2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.6 & 0.3 & 0.1 & 0 \\ 0.5 & 0.37 & 0.13 & 0 \\ 0.67 & 0.13 & 0.2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Index membership degree:

$$Z_1 = W_1 \cdot R_1 = (0.6333 \quad 0.2605 \quad 0.1062) \begin{bmatrix} 0.47 & 0.3 & 0.23 & 0 \\ 0.33 & 0.53 & 0.13 & 0 \\ 0.43 & 0.37 & 0.2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$= (0.411 \quad 0.367 \quad 0.201 \quad 0)$$

$$Z_2 = W_2 \cdot R_2 = (0.1932 \quad 0.7235 \quad 0.0833) \begin{bmatrix} 0.6 & 0.3 & 0.1 & 0 \\ 0.5 & 0.37 & 0.13 & 0 \\ 0.67 & 0.13 & 0.2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$= (0.533 \quad 0.336 \quad 0.130 \quad 0)$$

Taking the above evaluation vector as the company's comprehensive evaluation matrix, the final comprehensive evaluation result is:

$$Z_a = W \cdot R_a = (0.1667 \quad 0.8334) \begin{bmatrix} 0.533 & 0.336 & 0.130 & 0 \\ 0.411 & 0.367 & 0.201 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$= (0.513 \quad 0.341 \quad 0.143 \quad 0)$$

Similarly, the comprehensive evaluation results obtained by judging the various indicators of the other six companies are as follows:

(1) Each index in Shangying Company is evaluated, and a fuzzy evaluation matrix of two first-level indexes is obtained:

$$R_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.63 & 0.23 & 0.13 & 0 \\ 0.27 & 0.5 & 0.23 & 0 \\ 0.57 & 0.33 & 0.1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.43 & 0.37 & 0.2 & 0 \\ 0.3 & 0.4 & 0.3 & 0 \\ 0.27 & 0.37 & 0.2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Index membership degree: $Z_1 = (0.467 \quad 0.311 \quad 0.153 \quad 0)$ $Z_2 = (0.323 \quad 0.392 \quad 0.272 \quad 0)$

The final comprehensive evaluation results of this company are: $Z_b = (0.347 \quad 0.379 \quad 0.252 \quad 0)$

(2) Each index in EVA OUXIU Company is evaluated, and a fuzzy evaluation matrix of the first-level index is obtained:

$$R_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.37 & 0.47 & 0.17 & 0 \\ 0.5 & 0.23 & 0.27 & 0 \\ 0.2 & 0.37 & 0.43 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3 & 0.43 & 0.27 & 0 \\ 0.7 & 0.27 & 0.03 & 0 \\ 0.53 & 0.23 & 0.23 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Index membership degree: $Z_1 = (0.334 \quad 0.397 \quad 0.224 \quad 0)$ $Z_2 = (0.608 \quad 0.280 \quad 0.093 \quad 0)$

The final comprehensive evaluation results of this company are: $Z_c = (0.562 \quad 0.300 \quad 0.115 \quad 0)$

(3) Judge each index in Bech-Ding, and get the fuzzy evaluation matrix of the first-level index:

$$R_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.43 & 0.23 & 0.33 & 0 \\ 0.37 & 0.43 & 0.2 & 0 \\ 0.2 & 0.47 & 0.33 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.37 & 0.23 & 0 \\ 0.3 & 0.5 & 0.2 & 0 \\ 0.3 & 0.53 & 0.17 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Index membership degree: $Z_1 = (0.390 \quad 0.308 \quad 0.296 \quad 0)$ $Z_2 = (0.319 \quad 0.477 \quad 0.203 \quad 0)$

The final comprehensive evaluation results of this company are: $Z_d = (0.331 \quad 0.449 \quad 0.219 \quad 0)$

(4) Each index in Shangyue-E Company is evaluated, and the fuzzy evaluation matrix of the first-level index is obtained:

$$R_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3 & 0.43 & 0.23 & 0 \\ 0.53 & 0.3 & 0.13 & 0 \\ 0.2 & 0.4 & 0.4 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.6 & 0.27 & 0.13 & 0 \\ 0.27 & 0.43 & 0.3 & 0 \\ 0.3 & 0.43 & 0.27 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Index membership degree: $Z_1 = (0.256 \quad 0.471 \quad 0.271 \quad 0)$ $Z_2 = (0.450 \quad 0.261 \quad 0.289 \quad 0)$

The final comprehensive evaluation results of this company are: $Z_e = (0.338 \quad 0.398 \quad 0.257 \quad 0)$

(5) Each index in Ditizi-ji company is evaluated, and the fuzzy evaluation matrix of the first-level index is obtained:

$$R_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3 & 0.5 & 0.2 & 0 \\ 0.13 & 0.43 & 0.43 & 0 \\ 0.3 & 0.4 & 0.3 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.27 & 0.33 & 0.4 & 0 \\ 0.5 & 0.23 & 0.27 & 0 \\ 0.43 & 0.37 & 0.2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Index membership degree: $Z_1 = (0.256 \quad 0.471 \quad 0.271 \quad 0)$ $Z_2 = (0.450 \quad 0.261 \quad 0.289 \quad 0)$

The final comprehensive evaluation results of this company are: $Z_f = (0.418 \quad 0.296 \quad 0.286 \quad 0)$

(6) Each index in the white-collar-Geng company is evaluated, and the fuzzy evaluation matrix of the first-level index is obtained:

$$R_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.53 & 0.3 & 0.17 & 0 \\ 0.2 & 0.3 & 0.5 & 0 \\ 0.13 & 0.27 & 0.6 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.37 & 0.23 & 0.4 & 0 \\ 0.17 & 0.3 & 0.53 & 0 \\ 0.53 & 0.3 & 0.17 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Index membership degree: $Z_1 = (0.402 \quad 0.297 \quad 0.302 \quad 0)$ $Z_2 = (0.239 \quad 0.286 \quad 0.475 \quad 0)$

The final comprehensive evaluation results of this company are: $Z_j = (0.266 \quad 0.288 \quad 0.446 \quad 0)$

Comprehensive evaluation

In order to evaluate the best quality of the seven brand thin suits, the quantitative score of the comment set is calculated as the specific score value, using the following formula:

$$W_p = \sum_{k=1}^m z_{pk} y_k, P=A, B, C, D \quad m=4,$$

$$y_k = (\text{excellent, good, moderate, difference number}) \quad (5)$$

Can draw: $W_a = 8.716$, $W_b = 8.014$, $W_c = 8.71$, $W_d = 8.216$, $W_e = 8.106$, $W_f = 8.264$,
 $W_j = 7.640$

DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis of the overall evaluation results

In summary, this article uses the AHP method to obtain the weight value of the clothing quality evaluation index, and then combines the membership results of the fuzzy evaluation to perform compound calculations, and obtains the final fuzzy comprehensive evaluation results of the seven brand thin suits. The final calculation results The ranking results of the thin suit quality of seven brands can be obtained intuitively as shown in Table 6:

Table 6 Ranking of thin suit quality of seven brands

Rank	First	Second	Third	fourth	fifth	Sixth	Seventh
Brand	JIAFEN	EVA OUXIU	DITIZI	Ibec	Sunview	Shangying	WHITE COLLAR

Analyzing the results, we can get: The quality evaluation of the thin suit of Jiafen business women's clothing is 8.716, the score is the highest, and its comprehensive quality and cost performance are the best, whether it is the design process of the clothing itself or its value in the society. Welcomed and recognized by the majority of white-collar women. Yihua Ouxiu can contend with Jiafen. Their score difference can be equal to the same amount, and they can also meet the various needs of white-collar women. Compared with other business women's clothing brands, the overall quality is slightly inferior to Jiafen and Yihua Ouxiu. Among them, the white-collar brand has the lowest score, and all aspects of the quality of the thin suit need to be improved.

Analysis of the comprehensive evaluation of the brand itself

Reviewing the comprehensive evaluation results of each brand, it can be seen that these seven brands selected by the public are veritable brand clothing. The quality of the thin suits is affirmed by everyone, and the Chinese people have not been disappointed. According to the observation of the above comprehensive evaluation results, it can be seen that:

(1) Both Jiafen and Yihua Ouxiu's maximum ratings in the reviews are on the excellent rating, but Yihua Ouxiu's own excellent rating weight is higher than that of Jiafen, and the comprehensive score after the compound calculation is a little worse. The reason is that Jiafen's good and mid-level reviews are both higher than Yihua Ouxiu. Everyone's evaluation of Jiafen is slightly pertinent, and the evaluation opinions are relatively concentrated, while for Yihua Ouxiu, the evaluation is more scattered and will be larger difference.

(2) The pros and cons of the other five brands are relatively average, and the weight gap between the reviews is relatively small. Moreover, the largest results in the reviews did not surpass Jiafen and Yihua Ouxiu, indicating that there is still a certain strength gap between the brands, and their quality has not reached the level that customers prefer.

Analysis of each evaluation index of the brand

According to the calculation results of the membership degree of each evaluation index of each brand and the final evaluation result, it can be seen that the indicators that each brand considers the design and development direction of the thin suit are different. The two brands of Shangying and Ditz focus on

the development of the design process of the clothing itself, which is its own index. The other five brands focus on reflecting the social value that clothing brings to people, which is the social index. Brands that value self-centeredness in social indicators will be recognized by customers and ranked high. However, although Ditz is excellent, it will pay more attention to its own process indicators in the design and development of business thin suits. Obviously, the overall quality of brand clothing cannot be grasped by a single factor. Any factor has its own value. Affect the success and failure of a brand.

Combining their fuzzy matrices, select the most frequent value among the excellent grades, analyze the basic positioning and design focus indicators of each brand for business thin suits on its own and social indicators and summarize the following table 7.

Table 7 Summary of indicators focused on the design of thin suits by brands

Brand	Self index	Social indicators
JIAFEN	Fabric comfort	Style pertinence
EVA OUXIU	Color matchin	Egocentricity
DITIZI	Clothing accessories	Egocentricity
Ibec	Clothing accessories	Style pertinence
Sunview	Fabric comfort	Rigorous fashion
Shangying	Fabric comfort	Rigorous fashion
WHITE COLLAR	Fabric comfort	Style pertinence

It can be seen that the Jiafen brand and the comparable Yihua Ouxiu brand have their own design development characteristics and did not choose the same direction to compete. For the next five companies, Ditz ranked first. It focused on self-centered indicators, which can be said to account for a large part of the reason. Being able to realize that seeking new bright spots and being different from others in the comparable brand competition is also a magic weapon for defeating the enemy.

CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

This article uses a combination of analytic hierarchy process and fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method to evaluate and analyze the quality of the thin suits of seven domestic brands of business women's clothing. The weight of each index obtained by the analytic hierarchy process knows that the comfort of the fabric in the own index that affects the quality of clothing and the self-centeredness in the social index are two very important factors. White-collar women will make decisions based on these two indicators when choosing business wear. According to the calculation results, the two brands of Jiafen and Yihua Ouxiu are good choices for thin suits, and they can be well matched in all aspects. The design takes into account the psychological and physiological needs of white-collar women. White-collar brands are at a disadvantage here. The pursuit of the quality of thin suits needs to be further explored. Other brands need to improve the quality of clothing.

From the perspective of the research process, the reason why the brand can be successful is that it has undergone rigorous and rigorous social investigations, and can meet customer needs in a timely manner, provide customers with the latest fashion indicators, and lead the industry trend at the forefront. Therefore, each successful brand has its own market research team, design innovation team, and sales operation team to support them to discover the focus of their own brand clothing design and the targeted groups they want to grasp. For the quantitative results calculated in this paper based on incomplete data, it is not enough to draw this conclusion with a very positive attitude, and it is obviously lacking to directly determine the quality of a brand's clothing through only one type of clothing. To draw detailed and accurate conclusions inevitably requires more data and strong theoretical support. However, in view of the limited level of my research, various factors will not be considered comprehensively, and the investigation of the market is not very sufficient, so I just provide you with a reference. I hope to improve my ability in the future and continue to improve and give better opinions.

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